

DAMPING MATERIALS FOR SPACECRAFT VIBRATION CONTROL

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ABSTRACT

Newly developed constrained shear damping materials for spacecraft vibration control are epoxy based polymers. These materials show high damping capability ($\tan \delta$ max=1.3-1.8) and have low outgassing (TML<1%) in a space environment. Damping material SS-37 was applied to the "Yo-Yo" bracket in the 11th scientific satellite ASTRO-C (Japan).

INTRODUCTION

A significant number of spacecraft failures have been related to severe vibrations during launch and ground tests. Therefore, vibration reduction by applying viscoelastic damping treatments are necessary for increasing spacecraft reliability. [1] For damping space-compatible materials, properties required are high damping capability and low outgassing in a space environment. The reason is that high damping capability results in a low damping-treatment per weight. Also, low outgassing means that no cloud is formed to cause damage to optical sensor and solar cells. So, conventional damping materials can't be immediately applied to spacecraft structure.

This paper presents the design and development of damping space-compatible materials, and their application for the scientific satellite ASTRO-C.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Three different kinds of epoxy resin were used as viscoelastic materials. They are diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DEBA), diglycidyl ether of alkanediol oligomer (DEAO), and diglycidyl ether of branched alkanediol oligomer (DEAO-B). The structural formulas for DEAO and DEAO-B are shown in Figure 1. Two acid anhydrides were used as curing agents, phthalic anhydride derivative (PAD), and maleic anhydride derivative (MAD). Unreactive and reactive plasticizers were used for obtaining lower glass transition temperature (T_g). The former plasticizer was aromatic compounds oligomer (ACO). The latter plasticizer was polysulfide oligomer (PSO). These compounds were cured at 120°C for 3 hours.

Dynamic mechanical properties were determined, using a conventional force-vibration method, under tensile deformation. (VES-HC, IWAMOTO SEISAKUSHO CO., JAPAN)

For evaluating outgassing, following ASTM E 595-77 recommendation, two parameters were measured at 125°C and 10^{-6} torr for 24 hours; total mass loss (TML) and collected volatile condensable materials (CVCM). On the other hand, the mass-loss steps were evaluated to investigate the gas generating mechanism. Mass - loss (ML) data were determined by thermogravimetry (TG) instrument. (TG-40, SHIMAZU Co., JAPAN)

Vibration damping properties were measured using the composite beam test method. The composite beam, suspended at its nodal point, was composed of an aluminum beam (300×32×5 mm) and damping material. Damping loss factor η at the various natural frequencies of the composite beam were found by the half-power bandwidth.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The two basic forms of viscoelastic damping are extensional and constrained shear categories. Constrained shear damping is suitable for application to spacecraft structure. The shear damping is generally more

efficient than extensional damping treatment, on an equal-weight comparison.

In constrained shear damping, loss factor η depends on loss tangent ($\tan \delta$) for the damping (viscoelastic) material. [2] Therefore, viscoelastic materials are required that have high $\tan \delta$ at the desired temperature.

Table 1 Damping properties of DEBA-ACO systems (cured with PAD)

Sample	L(Å)	w(%)	E'g(Pa)	E'r(Pa)	$\tan^*\delta_{\max}$	Tg+(°C)	$\sqrt{E'g/E'r}$
A	20.4	0	1.4×10^9	1.6×10^7	1.0	170	10
B	20.4	33	1.9×10^9	6.5×10^6	1.1	115	17
C	20.4	50	1.8×10^9	3.3×10^6	1.2	80	23
D	55.4	50	2.0×10^9	1.3×10^6	1.5	55	39

- L: network chain mean length. (by simple estimation)
 w; plasticizer weight fraction.
 *; measured at 96 cps.
 +; determined by temperature for $\tan \delta$ maximum.

Tan δ maximum and Chemical Structure

Dynamic mechanical properties are explained by the simple three-element model, as shown in Figure 2. In addition to cyclic stress $\tan \delta$ is expressed as;

$$\tan \delta(\omega) = \frac{\omega \eta E'g'^2}{E'g'E'r(E'g' + E'r) + \omega^2 \eta^2 E'g'} \quad (1)$$

where $E'g'$ is the storage modulus for glassy plateau, $E'r$ is the storage modulus for rubbery plateau, ω is circular frequency, and η is viscous damping coefficient. $\tan \delta$ maximum in the frequency region is expressed as;

$$\tan \delta_{\max}(w) = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{E'g'}{E'r}} \quad (E'g' \gg E'r) \quad (2)$$

Based on time (frequency)-temperature superposition principles, the $\tan \delta$ maximum in the frequency region is equivalent to that in the temperature region, i.e.

$$\tan \delta_{\max}(w) = \tan \delta_{\max}(T) \quad (3)$$

The dynamic properties for plasticized and unplasticized DEBA epoxy resin are listed in Table 1. Curing agent PAD and unreactive plasticizer

ACO were used. $\tan \delta$ maximum increases and glass-transition temperature (T_g) lowers with increasing plasticizer content (w) and the mean length of the network chain (L). Figure 3 shows $\tan \delta$ maximum and $\sqrt{E_g/E_r}$ in these materials. The data shown by the solid line was calculated from Eq. (2). The discrepancy between theory and experiment is due to one relaxation mechanism in the three-element model.

The experimental values are proportional to $\sqrt{E_g/E_r}$. That is to say, $\tan \delta$ maximum increases with $\sqrt{E_g/E_r}$. Table 1 suggests that decreasing E_r contributes effectively to high $\tan \delta$ maximum. E_r decreases by (a) addition of plasticizer, (b) increasing the mean length (end to end) of the network chain, (c) applying flexible molecular chain, or (d) decreasing the cross-linking degree (decreasing the curing agent amount). [3.4]

Viscoelastic Damping Material Design

Reactive plasticizer PSO was used for obtaining lower T_g , because unreactive plasticizer evaporates easily in a space environment.

$\tan \delta$ values for DEBA-PSO (cured with PAD) are shown in Figure 4. The amount of PAD was 70% of stoichiometric content. $\tan \delta$ maximum values in these materials are larger than that for unplasticized DEBA, A. T_g is shifted to a lower temperature, from 55°C at 24.5% (w) content to 25°C at 47% (w). These T_g temperatures are also lower than those of DEBA-ACO, due to decreasing the cross-linking degree. Since vibration reduction for the spacecraft, prior to orbiting, is required at room temperature region, material with 47% PSO content was applicable as damping material (SS-37). $\tan \delta$ maximum for this material is about 1.3.

DEAO epoxy resin, that has a flexible molecular structure, was studied, for obtaining larger $\tan \delta$ maximum. Figure 5 shows temperature dependence for the $\tan \delta$. In DEAO cured with PAD, $\tan \delta$ maximum is 1.4, and T_g is 65°C. In DEAO-B, that has a more flexible chain, $\tan \delta$ maximum is larger and T_g is lower than for DEAO. $\tan \delta$ maximum is 1.7 and T_g is 50°C.

The lower T_g temperature is obtained by using MAD curing agent. MAD shifts T_g by approximately 20°C toward a lower temperature and has no effect on $\tan \delta$ maximum.

DEAO-B, cured with MAD, was applicable for spacecraft damping material (SS-53). T_g was adjusted to room temperature by decreasing the cross-linking degree. Dynamic mechanical properties are shown in Figure 6. This material has a large $\tan \delta$ maximum (≈ 1.8) at room temperature.

Figure 7 shows the mass-loss steps for SS-37 and DEBA using unreactive plasticizer (50%), C. ML data were measured at 125°C 10^{-4} torr by TG instrument. ML for material C is 40% at 8 hours. This value was produced by unreactive plasticizer volatilization. On the other hand, ML for SS-37 is about 1%. Since the ML state is saturated with passing time, annealing in a vacuum environment results in lower outgassing. Therefore, material after annealing was applicable for spacecraft damping material.

TML and CVCM values for these materials are listed in table 2. In both materials, TML is less than 1%, and CVCM is less than 0.2%.

Table 2 SS-37 and SS-53 properties.

Sample	TML(%) ⁺	CVCM(%) ⁺	$\tan \delta_{\text{max}}$	$T_g(^{\circ}\text{C})$
SS-37	0.65	0.02	1.3	25
SS-53	0.42	0.14	1.8	15

+: evaluated by ASTM E 595-77.

*: measured at 96 cps.

Damping properties for SS-53 and SS-37 were studied. The thicknesses of aluminum base plate, damping material, and aluminum constraining plate are, 5mm, 1mm and 1mm, respectively. Figure 8 shows loss factor η . Both materials have high vibration damping capability. Loss factor η for SS-53 is greater than that for SS-37, due to having large $\tan \delta$ maximum. On an equal-damping capability, about 20% weight reduction was achieved, in comparison with conventional materials that have $\tan \delta = 1.0$.

Application for Satellite

Damping material SS-37 was applied to the "Yo-Yo" bracket mounted on scientific satellite ASTRO-C. "Yo-Yo" is used for despinning a rotating satellite body. Constraining plate and damping material thicknesses are 5mm and 18mm, respectively. (Figure 9) Figure 10 shows the ground test

results. Vibration level at resonant frequencies (180cps, 450cps) is reduced to half with damping treatment. [5]

SS-53, as well as SS-37, can be applied efficiently to spacecraft structure.

SUMMARY

Damping materials, that have large $\tan \delta$ maximum value and low outgassing, were obtained by decreasing the cross-linking degree, adding reactive plasticizer, and applying flexible molecular chain. $\tan \delta$ maximum values for SS-53 and SS-37 are 1.8 and 1.3, respectively. TML is less than 1% for both. These values show the possibility of successful application for spacecraft structure. Furthermore, quantitative design method will be studied.

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Figure 4 Temperature dependence for $\tan \delta$.
 DEBA (L=20.4A)-ACO systems. (cured with PAD)
 ○ (w=24.5%): ● (w=33.0%): ● (w=37.5%): ● (w=47.0%).

Figure 5 Temperature dependence for $\tan \delta$.
 ○ DEAO (L=17.8A) cured with PAD: ○ DEAO-B (L=17.8A) cured with PAD: ● DEAO-B (L=17.8A) cured with MAD.

Figure 6 Dynamic mechanical properties for SS-53.

Figure 7 Mass-loss steps. (ML time dependences)

Figure 8 SS-53 and SS-37 damping loss factors.

Figure 9 "Yo-Yo" bracket with damping materials.

Figure 10 "Yo-Yo" bracket acceleration response.
with damping treatment:
 —without damping treatment.